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Basic Contents of the Teaching of Political Theory at the University of Technology Today

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Abstract: Renovating the teaching method of political theory in current universities in Vietnam in general, including Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology in particular during the Fourth Industrial Revolution requires adapting the professional qualifications, political bravery, and professional ethics of each lecturer. The demand for learning political theory (Pol. Theory) expressed through indicators of learning perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors is not high. The need to learn Pol. Theory only really appears in students when they are fully and properly aware of the role and importance of Pol. Theory learning for the formation of their personality and the development of their socio-political capacity. For students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology today, improving thinking capacity is an indispensable capacity of each student in awareness and practical activities, which is a requirement of social practice for students today. The training of thinking capacity for Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology students through the study of Pol. Theory subjects will contribute to moral education, revolutionary ideals, lifestyles, and beliefs, giving students a strong stance in the face of all challenges, which is the premise for students to try to practice and study together to build the country for the goal of rich people, strong country,

democracy, justice, and civilization. The article analyzes and clarifies the issues related to the teaching of Pol. Theory subjects at the current technical university; some specific issues to help teach Pol. Theory subjects at Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology today.

Keywords: Political theory; lecturers; students; university; technical; Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology.

1. Introduction

In the current context, in the face of many intertwined challenges and difficulties of university teaching, it is necessary to fundamentally renovate the curriculum, content, and methods of political theory education according to the motto of science, practice, creativity, and modernity. This is an important theoretical basis for universities in Vietnam today to continue innovating in teaching political theory subjects, meeting the requirements of real life. For universities in the national education system in general, including technical universities, in particular, the teaching and learning of political theory (Pol. Theory) is important because these are the basic subjects in the content and training program, which have the function of equipping the worldview and scientific methodology, not only helping learners gain a comprehensive amount of knowledge but also making an important contribution to the formation and development of political capacity, political quality, ideology, morality, and lifestyle.

2. Contents

2.1. Overview of the achieved results

According to the regulations of the Ministry of Education and Training, Pol. Theory subjects taught at the undergraduate level are Marxist-Leninist philosophy, Marxist-Leninist political economy, scientific socialism, Ho Chi Minh's ideology, and the history of the Communist Party of Vietnam. These are generalized, abstract, partisan, and highly scientific subjects. Therefore, to teach Pol. Theory subjects well, lecturers must have a sharp political vision, a strong ideological stance, and knowledge of specialized and interdisciplinary knowledge; at the same time, they must comply with the principle of unity between theory and practice in both content and teaching methods. The overall goal of teaching Pol. Theory subjects are to help learners understand systematically and fundamentally the principles of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's ideology; and the views and lines of the Communist Party of Vietnam. From that theoretical ideological foundation, it helps learners have confidence in the Party's leadership, goals, and ideals, and at the same time, have a scientific methodology to apply the knowledge equipped to solving economic, political, cultural, and social issues according to the lines, policies, and laws of the Party and the State. The practice of teaching Pol. Theory subjects at technical universities have recently had a positive innovation, the quality of teaching Pol. Theory subjects have been constantly improved, making an important contribution to improving the quality of education and training. Technical universities have identified appropriate requirements and solutions to improve the teaching quality of Pol. Theory subjects; teaching methods according to the "scientific, practical, creative and modern motto" are thoroughly and

flexibly applied by lecturers according to each subject and training objectives for each specific subject and lesson, based on combining traditional teaching methods with modern teaching methods. The agreement between theory and practice in teaching Pol. Theory subjects have been carried out in a strict logical sequence from lecture preparation, lecture practice, seminar guidance, exchange, and practice to the organization of learning management. In general, the practice of teaching Pol. Theory subjects at technical universities in the past have achieved some results, basically:

Firstly, Pol. Theory education is closely led and directed by the leaders at technical universities. The Board of Rectors of technical universities regularly pays attention to leading, directing, and organizing the completion of the curriculum, renovating the content and syllabus, and diversifying teaching forms and methods. Focus on organizing and renovating the teaching management mechanism of Pol. Theory subjects. Pay attention to building and improving educational qualifications, developing teaching capacity, and theoretical research capacity, summarizing practical research and training, cultivating political qualities, ideology, ethics, stance, revolutionary views, vocational love, and aspiration to contribute to Pol. Theory lecturers. Paying attention to investment in building facilities, modernizing teaching media, developing library systems, materials for research, and teaching Pol. Theory.

Secondly, the quality of teaching staff and programs, contents, methods, forms, and means of Pol. Theory education is regularly improved and renewed. Most Pol. Theory lecturers have high political qualities, good ethics, a clean lifestyle, enthusiasm for the profession, and professional qualifications that meet the requirements of the current Pol. Theory education mission. The level of education is high, and the level of professional expertise is increasingly consolidated and developed. Some trainers quickly adapt to the process of training mode transformation, innovation, and access to advanced training programs. Many Pol. Theory lecturers actively explore, create, and self-train to improve their theoretical and practical knowledge and improve their qualifications in applying modern teaching methods and new forms of teaching organization. Most lecturers take advantage of the time when they are not in class to study science and prepare lessons. Thanks to the efforts of lecturers, Pol. Theory lectures become more attractive, stimulating students to be interested in studying, researching, and applying Pol. Theory knowledge in recognizing, interpreting, analyzing, and evaluating events and phenomena taking place in national and international political life, as well as applying Pol. Theory knowledge in learning and researching specialized subjects. In addition, Pol. Theory programs, contents, methods, forms, and means of education are constantly innovating. The continuous renovation of the program of Pol. Theory subjects demonstrate innovative thinking, and demanding attitudes, demonstrating the process of exploration and experimentation to have a standard program to achieve its necessary objectives, per the practice of undergraduate training, suitable for learners and teachers. However the continuous innovation process, including twists and turns and even backsliding, also shows inadequacies in leadership and direction, in theoretical thinking, and in the capacity to advise and develop programs and curricula of professional agencies and experts. On the other hand, at the current technical universities, the form of Pol. Theory education also has a lot of research, improvement, and creativity. Mainstream, extracurricular, and

self-education forms are applied, coordinated, and combined to suit each student and subject content. The method of evaluating teaching and learning results has also been innovated from the main method of essay examination to the technique of oral examination, multiple-choice examination, essay writing... or combining multiple-choice examination with essay examination, strengthening direct oral examination, encouraging essay writing, innovating the quality assessment of essays and dissertations... Pol. Theory educational media is also being equipped and improved by many universities in an increasingly complete, synchronous, and modern direction. All classrooms are connected to the Internet, and equipped with multi-purpose projectors, sound amplification devices, and many other modern teaching equipment, allowing Pol. Theory lecturers implement and apply active teaching methods and develop students' independent and creative thinking capacities.

2.2 Basic aspects that still exist in the Pol. Theory teaching process at technical universities

Unlike most other subjects, the change and development of knowledge of political theory subjects is often slow, so some students may think that they are too familiar, not new, not causing curiosity and interest. This is because the issues of the meaning and value of human life such as existence, morality, human life, justice, struggle, democracy, happiness, freedom, solidarity, and equality..., are always concerned. Political theory knowledge is slow to change because it is built on the process of research, theorization, and discussion in the community of researchers and scholars. The principles, categories, rules, views... are often highly abstract, strictly required for correctness, and do not accept contradictory or illogical information. Such knowledge must undergo extensive verification before it can be accepted. Therefore, if only based on personal reasoning, illogical explanations, lack of practical basis, and lack of science are not accepted. Meanwhile, students at technical universities (For example, Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology), all have quite high entry points compared to the general ground and have the capacity and level of thinking in general, in which logical thinking is good.

People who studied and did political theory work during each period often made new judgments and analyses. They present different views and arguments on issues of political theory. However, some basic principles, such as Party character in philosophy, materialist dialectical methodology in research, "immutability" such as "nation first, country first," class stance, etc., are unchanged. These principles have remained the same over time serving as the basis for thinking, discussing, and critiquing. These principles have remained the same over time serving as the basis for thinking, discussing, and critiquing. This is also the difficulty in shaping perception and thinking for technical students. In addition, a part of lecturers are accustomed to teaching in a method that focuses on theory, attaches importance to knowledge, emphasizes academics, ignores the association of theory with practice, does not apply information technology in teaching and learning, and does not focus on soft skills training for students. With such a method, it is possible to make technical students not interested in political theory subjects. Students in technical schools will find it difficult to find the attraction, value, and benefits of studying political theory with lecturers who use traditional methods as they have always used. Stemming from the above content, some specific issues to help teach political theory at Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology shortly will be:

Interested in creating a conducive learning environment.

For students at Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, lecturers should encourage interaction by promoting discussion, and group activities, encouraging the ability to solve problems, ask questions, and debate.

Focus on teamwork, discussion, debate, and asking questions.

It is necessary to create a discussion and debate environment to encourage students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology to think more deeply about the issues raised. Use open-ended questions to explore the diversity of opinions as well as to develop logical reasoning.

The content of the lecture relates to reality.

Lecturers using examples and practical contacts will make an important contribution to helping students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology understand how to present their ideas clearly and convincingly. When students see how their knowledge of political theory can be applied to real-life situations, they will develop their logical thinking and problem-solving abilities in real life.

Encourage critical thinking.

Encouraging critical thinking in the teaching of political theory subjects brings many benefits because creative thinking encourages students to seek and explore new aspects of theoretical knowledge, helping them not only deepen their understanding of the topic but also develop the ability to consider problems from many different angles, train their reasoning skills. Critical thinking will encourage students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology to seek knowledge in the learning process.

Conclusion

University students are the source of creating a team of socialist intellectuals, the future owners of the country. In the contents of education, training, and retraining for students, it is necessary to strengthen education on Pol. Theory to form for students a worldview of dialectical materialism, revolutionary humanism, scientific methodology, theoretical thinking, and political-practical thinking, creating resistance to wrong and hostile views, contributing to the comprehensive development of Vietnamese people, meeting the requirements of accelerating industrialization and modernization of the country and international integration, as well as the requirements of the current ideological and theoretical struggle. For students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, improving thinking capacity is an indispensable capacity of each student in awareness and practical activities, which is a requirement of social practice for current students. The training of thinking capacity for students of Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology through the study of political theory subjects will contribute to moral education, revolutionary ideals, lifestyle, and beliefs, giving students a firm stance in the face of all challenges, which is the premise for students to try to practice and study together to build the country for the goal of rich people, strong country, democracy, justice and civilization./.

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